

Assessment of knowledge and opinion towards microneedles technology among jordanian pharmacists

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Abstract

Background: Microneedles are an innovative, patient-friendly, minimally invasive, and self-administered drug delivery system that has garnered significant attention. This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge, awareness, and acceptance of Jordanian pharmacists toward microneedles and to identify associated predictors. During January and February 2023, a cross-sectional study using an online questionnaire was conducted in Jordan. Binary logistic regression analysis was employed to identify predictors of increased awareness of microneedles as a medication delivery system.

Results: A total of 474 pharmacists participated in the study, with 67.9% reporting familiarity with transdermal drug delivery. The most commonly cited source of information about microneedles was university education (85.1%). Nearly half (47.5%) of the pharmacists advised washing the application area with water or sterilizing it with an alcohol swab. The top three advantages of microneedles over other transdermal delivery systems were faster healing at the injection site (43.7%), ease of administration (41.1%), and painless delivery of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (40.7%). The pharmacists demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge about microneedles, with a mean knowledge score of 4.3 (SD 1.6) out of 7. Binary logistic regression analysis revealed that pharmacists with 5–10 years of experience were more likely to be knowledgeable about microneedles as a drug delivery system compared to others ($p \leq 0.01$).

Conclusion: Pharmacists showed a solid understanding of microneedle technology, yet certain knowledge gaps remain, particularly regarding the advantages, design, and applications of microneedles. Increased educational efforts are recommended to bridge these gaps and enhance pharmacists' competence in this area.

Strengths and limitations of this study:

- This study investigated the level of knowledge and awareness among 474 pharmacists in Jordan, who are employed across diverse sectors within the field of pharmacy.
- The existing body of academic literature concerning pharmacists' familiarity and understanding of microneedle technology is notably limited.
- The study was carried out using an online questionnaire, which has an unpredictable response rate.

Keywords

acceptance, drug delivery, Jordan, knowledge, microneedles, pharmacists

Introduction

Drug delivery systems have emerged as pivotal tools for ensuring the safe and effective administration of therapeutic agents (Allen and Cullis 2004). These systems play a crucial role in regulating drug release rates, overcoming challenging physiological barriers, and augmenting the efficacy of therapeutic compounds. Currently, the predominant routes of medication administration are oral and intravenous (IV) (Lu et al. 2020). Despite the advantages of the oral route, it presents considerable limitations (Vargason et al. 2021). Oral medications are exposed to gastrointestinal secretions and first-pass metabolism. Additionally, they pose challenges for paediatric populations, patients with swallowing difficulties, those with mental disorders, or individuals who are unconscious (Stuurman et al. 2013; Shepherd and Shepherd 2020). IV drug administration requires trained healthcare providers and facilities and can be inconvenient, affecting patient compliance. Approximately 10% of the population experiences varying degrees of needle phobia due to the painful nature of IV injections (Wani et al. 2014).

Alternatively, the transdermal route holds potential to overcome many limitations associated with oral and IV administration. This route offers noninvasive or minimally invasive drug delivery while avoiding first-pass metabolism and the gastrointestinal tract (Chappell 2015; Lou et al. 2023). Delivering molecules to the systemic circulation through the skin was approved in 1979. The USFDA approved the production of the first transdermal patch to deliver scopolamine for motion sickness (Nachum et al. 2006a). One transdermal patch per 2.2 years was approved between 1979 and 2002. In contrast, the rate of developing transdermal patches accelerated to one patch every 7.5 months between 2003 and 2007. This improvement indicates that transdermal drug delivery represents a promising delivery system, as the estimated rate is more than one billion patches every year (Williams 2003; Prausnitz and Langer 2008).

Microneedle (MN) technology represents a revolutionary transdermal drug delivery system. This technology has garnered significant attention for its patient-friendly, minimally invasive, and self-administered delivery approach (Nachum et al. 2006b). MNs are designed to be applied on the skin to deliver therapeutics locally or systemically (Williams 2003). They consist of an array of microscale needles (250–1000 μm) that bypass the stratum corneum (SC), forming microchannels in the skin layers to deliver therapeutics (Bereda 2023). MNs offer pain-free drug delivery since they are shorter than the nerves in the skin (Cvenkel and Kolko 2022). This groundbreaking technology was conceived in 1976 and was reported in research in 1998 (Jin et al. 2015; Ramöller et al. 2020). Since then, considerable interest has grown around MNs and their efficacy in delivering a wide array of therapeutic agents and drug molecules (Abu Ershaid et al. 2023).

In the event that this drug delivery system receives approval from regulatory agencies such as the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), pharmacists will need to be well-versed in counselling and advising patients on prop-

er administration techniques. Pharmacists will also need to be informed about precautions and labelling related to application frequency and potential drug interactions. Moreover, if pharmacists assume the role of primary prescribers, particularly for over-the-counter (OTC) medications, their responsibilities will significantly increase.

In this study, we aim to assess the level of awareness and acceptance of Jordanian pharmacists regarding MN technology and identify associated predictive factors.

Methods

Study design

From January to February 2023, a cross-sectional study was carried out among Jordanian pharmacists. The questionnaire was developed by the authors based on key points addressing pharmacists' level of knowledge and opinions regarding MN technology. In brief, the online questionnaire was conducted in the English language (English is the study language in Jordan) and included six knowledge questions and eight opinion questions. The questionnaire was validated by distributing it among experts in the pharmaceutical technology field and pharmacists from different fields, who were asked to answer and review it.

Data sources

Eligible pharmacists were invited to take part in the study through dedicated social media channels and Facebook groups tailored to the Jordanian pharmacist community. All pharmacists were invited to participate voluntarily in the research and, as such, were not required to provide formal informed consent. The introductory letter accompanying the questionnaire clearly explained the study's aims and objectives. The inclusion criteria for participation were as follows: (a) being a registered pharmacist possessing at least a diploma in pharmacy and (b) currently employed in Jordan. These inclusion criteria were explicitly emphasized in the introductory letter. The exclusion criterion was being unemployed.

Study population

The Raosoft® sample size calculator was used to estimate the representative sample size. For online questionnaires, the following formula: $n = P \times (1 - P) \times z^2/d^2$, is commonly applied. With a margin of error (d) of 5%, a confidence level of 95%, and a response distribution (P) of 50%, the online calculator estimated a minimum recommended sample size of 379 participants (Qadus et al. 2022; Ayoub et al. 2023; Hammour et al. 2023). The actual sample size was 474 pharmacists.

Statistical analysis

SPSS software, version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA), was used to analyze the data. Continuous variables were reported using the mean (SD). Categorical

variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Binary logistic regression analysis was employed to identify predictors of increased awareness of microneedles as a medication delivery system. The sample's average knowledge score was used to establish the cut-off for the dummy variable in the logistic regression. A 95% confidence interval ($p < 0.05$) and a 5% level of significance were used to illustrate the statistical significance of the data.

Patient and public involvement

None.

Abbreviations

MN: microneedle; IV: intravenous; SC: stratum corneum; FDA: Food and Drug Administration.

Results

Participants' demographic characteristics

A total of 474 pharmacists were included in this study. More than half (56.5%) reported holding a bachelor's degree in pharmacy. Around 41.0% of the participating

pharmacists reported having less than 2 years of experience. Almost one-third (34.6%) reported working at an independent community pharmacy. The vast majority (92.6%) reported graduating from a local university. Around 42.0% reported having worked in their current practice settings for a period of 1–5 years. For further details on the demographic characteristics of the study participants, refer to Table 1.

Awareness of microneedles as a transdermal drug delivery system

More than half of the participating pharmacists (67.9%) reported that they were familiar with delivering a drug to the blood via the skin, such as through transdermal drug delivery. The most commonly cited source of information about MNs was university education (85.1%). When participants were asked about the number of transdermal drugs available in the Jordanian market, 41.0% reported that 1–3 drugs are available. The majority of participants (74.3%) reported being familiar with MN terminology. The most commonly cited source of their familiarity with MNs was university education (68.2%). The majority of participants (84.0%) reported supporting the commercialization and FDA approval of MNs as a new transdermal drug delivery system in Jordan. Table 2 presents participants' awareness of MNs as a transdermal drug delivery system.

Table 1. Participants' demographic characteristics.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
What degree in pharmacy do you have?		
Diploma	83	17.5%
Bachelor's degree in pharmacy	268	56.5%
Bachelor's degree in doctor of pharmacy	39	8.2%
Master's degree in pharmacy	57	12.0%
PhD in pharmacy	27	5.7%
How many years of experience do you have?		
0–2 years	194	40.9%
2–5 years	113	23.8%
5–10 years	78	16.5%
More than 10 years	89	18.8%
In which sector of pharmacy do you currently work?		
Independent community pharmacy	164	34.6%
Pharmaceutical company	77	16.2%
Chain pharmacy	76	16.0%
Hospital pharmacy	55	11.6%
Government facilities	15	3.2%
Military healthcare provision settings	7	1.5%
Others	80	16.9%
Country of education for your latest degree?		
Local university	439	92.6%
Foreign university (outside Jordan)	35	7.4%
Experience in practicing settings		
Less than one year	147	31.0%
1–5 years	199	42.0%
6–10 years	62	13.1%
More than 10 years	66	13.9%

Table 2. Awareness of participants about microneedles as a transdermal drug delivery system.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Are you familiar with delivering a drug to the blood via the skin (transdermal drug delivery)?		
Yes	322	67.9%
If yes, what is your source of information? (more than one answer could be chosen)		
University course/education	274	85.1%
Internet	91	28.3%
Pharmaceutical company medical representatives	74	23.0%
Social media	56	17.4%
Others	89	27.6%
How many transdermal drugs are available in the Jordanian market?		
Zero	60	12.7%
1–3 drugs	194	40.9%
4–7 drugs	124	26.2%
More than 7 drugs	96	20.3%
Are you familiar with this terminology (microneedles)?		
Yes	352	74.3%
If yes, what is your source of information? (more than one answer could be chosen)		
University course/education	240	68.2%
Internet	101	28.7%
Social media	70	19.9%
Pharmaceutical company medical representatives	59	16.8%
Others	98	27.8%
Do you support the commercialization and FDA approval of microneedles as a new transdermal drug delivery system in Jordan?		
Yes	398	84.0%

Knowledge of microneedles as a transdermal drug delivery system

Table 3 describes participants' responses to knowledge items regarding MNs as a transdermal drug delivery system. Almost half of the participating pharmacists (47.5%) reported that washing the area of application with water or sterilizing it with an alcohol swab is the main patient advice they would provide if commercial MNs were available. Around 40.0% reported that age is irrelevant for MN prescribing. Almost 48.0% reported that patients with injection phobia, those suffering from chronic illnesses such as hypertension and emphysema, and those experiencing acute illness or temporary pain such as headache would benefit most from the merits of MNs. Almost half of the participants (49.8%) reported that MNs would increase patient cooperation (adherence) with medication. The

three most commonly cited advantages of MNs over other available transdermal delivery systems were faster healing at the injection site, ease of administration, and painless delivery of the active pharmaceutical ingredient, accounting for 43.7%, 41.1%, and 40.7%, respectively.

Predictors of better knowledge of microneedles as drug delivery system

The participating pharmacists showed a moderate level of knowledge about MNs as a drug delivery system, with a mean knowledge score of 4.3 (SD 1.6) out of 7, equal to 61.4% of the maximum obtainable score. Binary logistic regression analysis showed that pharmacists with 5–10 years of experience were more likely to be knowledgeable about MNs as a drug delivery system compared to others ($p \leq 0.01$). In Table 4, "How many years of experience

Table 3. Knowledge of microneedles as a transdermal drug delivery system.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
If there are commercial microneedles, what is the main patient advice you would provide to educate your patient?*		
Wash the area of application with water or sterilize it with an alcohol swab	225	47.5%
Press the microneedle patch gently upon application to ensure it penetrates the skin	130	27.4%
Hydrate the application area with suitable w/o emulsion	58	12.2%
No need for patient education because it is simply a patch	61	12.9%
What age category may suit patients for prescribing microneedles? (more than one answer could be chosen)*		
Adults	236	49.8%
Geriatric	110	23.2%
Paediatrics	83	17.5%
Age is irrelevant to this matter	191	40.3%
Who do you think will best benefit from the merit of microneedles?*		
Patients with injection phobia	93	19.6%
Patients with chronic illness such as hypertension and emphysema	87	18.4%
Patients with acute illness or temporary pain such as headache	66	13.9%
All of the mentioned options are equally possible	228	48.1%
Upon reading/hearing the term microneedles, as a pharmacist, what possibilities come to mind? (More than one answer could be chosen)		
Increased patient cooperation (adherence) to medication	236	49.8%
Ease of use compared to other dosage forms	205	43.2%
Improved management of polypharmacy using this technology	180	38.0%
A technique that may or may not work like every other technology	87	18.4%
In your opinion, what is the best advantage of microneedles over other available transdermal delivery systems? (more than one answer could be chosen)		
Faster healing at the injection site	207	43.7%
Ease of administration	195	41.1%
Painless administration of the active pharmaceutical ingredient	193	40.7%
No fear of needle	174	36.7%
Large molecules can be administered	151	31.9%
Rapid drug delivery achieved by coupling microneedles with an electrically controlled micro-pump	147	31.0%
Rate of drug delivery can be controlled	142	30.0%
Specific skin area can be targeted for desired drug delivery	128	27.0%
Enhanced drug efficacy may result in dose reduction	124	26.2%
Decreased microbial penetration	108	22.8%
Good tolerability without long-term oedema or erythema	104	21.9%
Microneedles compared to other available transdermal delivery systems (e.g., patch or gel) are more effective: (Yes)*	365	80.6%
Microneedles enhance the transdermal penetration of various types of molecules: (Yes)*	382	80.6%
Microneedles can deliver drugs into the systemic circulation painlessly: (Yes)*	375	79.1%
Microneedles can be self-administered: (Yes)*	345	72.8%
Do you think microneedles will be hard to use if the patient suffers from muscle problems (e.g., osteoarthritis)? (Yes)	236	49.8%
Microneedles can cause mild irritation or erythema; will these raise your concerns? (Yes)	324	68.4%

* Items used to calculate participants' knowledge score.

do you have?” represents total years of experience in the field. On the other hand, “Experience in practice settings” represents years of practice in specific settings such as community pharmacy or hospital pharmacy. Other demographic characteristics of the participating pharmacists did not show a statistically significant difference ($p \geq 0.05$).

Table 4. Predictors of better knowledge of microneedles as a drug delivery system.

Variable	Odds ratio (95% confidence interval)	p-value
What degree in pharmacy do you have?		
Diploma (reference group)	1.00	
Bachelor's degree in pharmacy	1.05 (0.73–1.52)	0.778
Bachelor's degree in doctor of pharmacy	1.60 (0.82–3.11)	0.167
Master's degree in pharmacy	1.32 (0.76–2.30)	0.329
PhD in pharmacy	1.88 (0.84–4.21)	0.122
How many years of experience do you have?		
0–2 years (reference group)	1.00	
2–5 years	0.77 (0.50–1.18)	0.228
5–10 years	2.03 (1.23–3.34)	0.006*
More than 10 years	1.56 (0.98–2.49)	0.061
In which sector of pharmacy do you currently work?		
Independent community pharmacy (reference group)	1.00	
Pharmaceutical company	1.08 (0.66–1.77)	0.748
Chain pharmacy	0.64 (0.39–1.05)	0.074
Hospital pharmacy	1.13 (0.64–1.97)	0.682
Government facilities	0.71 (0.25–2.01)	0.515
Military healthcare provision settings	0.42 (0.08–2.20)	0.307
Country of education for your latest degree?		
Local university (reference group)	1.00	
Foreign university (outside Jordan)	1.03 (0.87–1.23)	0.702
Experience in practice settings:		
Less than one year (reference group)	1.00	
1–5 years	1.03 (0.72–1.48)	0.873
6–10 years	1.08 (0.63–1.84)	0.775
More than 10 years	1.44 (0.85–2.42)	0.176

* $p \leq 0.01$

Discussion

In light of the key findings from this study, several noteworthy observations can be made. Firstly, more than half of the participating pharmacists (67.9%) reported familiarity with the concept of transdermal drug delivery, while 74.3% were familiar with microneedle technology. It is encouraging that a significant majority of pharmacists exhibited a notable level of familiarity with the terminology associated with transdermal drug delivery and microneedles. This foundation of knowledge is instrumental in facilitating their potential integration into clinical practice. Secondly, the most commonly cited source of information about MNs was university education (85.1%). This underscores the importance of academic institutions in shaping awareness and

understanding of emerging drug delivery technologies within the pharmaceutical community.

Furthermore, 47.5% of participating pharmacists reported that advising patients to wash the area of application with water or sterilize it with an alcohol swab was their main counseling advice. This heightened awareness aligns with the essential need to minimize the risk of microbial contamination associated with MN use. It is worth noting that, at present, there are no definitive guidelines provided by regulatory bodies such as the Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) or the United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) regarding the utilization of MNs. In light of these findings, it is strongly recommended that relevant regulatory institutions take proactive steps to issue comprehensive guidelines. Such guidelines should clarify the recommended patient advice and counseling for the adoption of MN technology as an innovative drug delivery system. These would enhance the standardization of practices and ensure the safety and efficacy of MN utilization in healthcare.

Moreover, almost 48.0% of pharmacists reported that microneedles may be highly beneficial for various patient conditions, including individuals with injection phobia, those managing chronic conditions such as hypertension and emphysema, and those experiencing acute or temporary pain, such as headache. Injection phobia is a documented psychiatric disorder affecting 3–4% of the United States population, characterized by serious fear, avoidance, dizziness, and loss of consciousness (Abdelghany et al. 2023). This phobia impacts therapeutic outcomes, as it may discourage patients from following their therapy plans. In a study in Canada, around 8% of children and 7% of adults reported that their injection phobia was the reason for refusing vaccination (Taddio et al. 2012). The incorporation of MN technology may potentially mitigate the prevalence of injection phobia due to the small size of these micro-needles compared to conventional hypodermic needles, rendering them virtually imperceptible to patients. MNs are designed to puncture only the outermost layer of the skin, the *stratum corneum* (SC), without penetrating deeper skin layers (Abu Ershaid et al. 2024). Consequently, this straightforward, painless, and minimally invasive method of drug administration has the potential to greatly enhance the overall patient experience and promote adherence to treatment regimens (Paredes et al. 2021).

Interestingly, a recent survey among the Jordanian public aimed at assessing the prevalence of needle phobia revealed that approximately 28.5% of participants acknowledged experiencing needle phobia, while 43.5% reported varying levels of fear associated with needles (Abdelghany et al. 2023). The study also investigated the level of familiarity and acceptance of MNs among the Jordanian public, revealing a preference for MNs over conventional needles. This preference highlights the potential of MNs to alleviate injection phobia and garner positive reception from patients in drug delivery contexts.

MNs can be applied to several uses, as previously mentioned in the survey. Pharmacists should be educated about the possible applications of this technology. MNs have been

evaluated for chronic conditions such as hypertension, cancer, and rheumatoid arthritis (Chen et al. 2022; Ganeson et al. 2023; Khalid et al. 2023). Additionally, this technology has been applied to acute conditions such as pain, vaccination, and inflammation (Vicente-Perez et al. 2017; Xie et al. 2017). Although 52% of the participating pharmacists did not agree that the use of MNs is suitable for chronic disease, the literature has shown the feasibility of delivering such medications successfully (Zhao et al. 2021).

This collective perspective underscores the potential broad-reaching impact of microneedles in diverse clinical scenarios. Additionally, it is noteworthy that nearly half of participants anticipated that the introduction of microneedles could lead to enhanced patient cooperation and adherence to medication regimens, reflecting a positive outlook toward the potential of this innovative drug delivery system. Medication adherence, defined as patients taking medications as prescribed by the prescriber (Gu et al. 2025), plays a substantial role in enhancing clinical treatment outcomes. The painless and minimally invasive drug administration offered by MN technology may improve the patient experience and enhance adherence to medications. Moreover, reducing dosing frequency and increasing time intervals between doses can enhance adherence (Coleman et al. 2012). Long-acting MN patches are designed to be applied once every several days or weeks, potentially improving patient adherence (Abu Ershaid et al. 2023). These advantages align with the goal of enhancing patients' overall experiences and treatment outcomes, emphasizing the prospective significance of microneedle technology within the pharmaceutical domain. The ongoing advancement of drug delivery systems into user-friendly dosage forms that simplify medication administration is an active area of research (Ershaid et al. 2024). Among these advancements, microneedles stand out as a pioneering technology that has garnered significant attention but has not yet reached full commercialization (Tarawneh et al. 2025). This technology has shown substantial promise in effectively delivering a wide range of medications, including hydrophobic and hydrophilic compounds, both high and low doses, controlled prescription drugs, and over-the-counter medications (Walters and Lane 2020). Almost 40.0% of participating pharmacists reported that age is irrelevant for MN prescribing. Several applications of MNs across different age categories have been reported. The European Paediatric Drug Legislation highlighted the need for developing painless, minimally invasive, and age-appropriate drug delivery systems (Van Riet-Nales et al. 2017). Taking advantage of the small size of the MN array, this technology has been applied to deliver insulin for children to ensure painless administration (Zuberi et al. 2020). Additionally, MNs for paediatrics have been reported to deliver various therapeutics, including methotrexate and antirheumatic drugs (Shende and Salunke 2019; Gorantla et al. 2022).

MN technology can also benefit both adults and geriatric populations. MNs have been introduced for several applications in these age categories, including cancer therapy, non-steroidal anti-inflammatories, vaccines, and anaesthetics (Paredes et al. 2021; Sen et al. 2025). These findings suggest that MN technology can be applied across

different age categories (children, adults, and geriatric). However, a few considerations should be kept in mind when applying MNs for paediatrics, such as ensuring full MN insertion and maintaining the small size of the patch.

Pharmacists play a significant role in patient care by not only dispensing medications but also providing essential counselling to patients (Taybeh et al. 2020; Naser and Abu Sbeat 2022). The education of these healthcare professionals in emerging technologies is paramount (Naser et al. 2020). Enhanced awareness among pharmacists can serve as a catalyst for fostering patient acceptance of such innovative advancements (Ahmed and Tamim 2025). Microneedle technology, for instance, stands as a novel and minimally invasive drug delivery system with the potential to improve the quality of patients' lives and promote better adherence to medication regimens.

Lastly, the most commonly reported advantages of microneedles over existing transdermal delivery methods include the promise of expedited healing at the injection site, the simplicity of administration, and the virtually painless delivery of active pharmaceutical components. Around 43.7% of pharmacists believed MNs would show a faster healing rate at the injection site. Furthermore, MNs provide a simple alternative for medications that require trained professionals for administration. MNs can be self-administered and require no professional or specific healthcare facility. In this study, 41.1% of participants agreed with the ease of administration.

MNs entered research in 1998, and since then, an increasing number of studies and evaluations have been reported (Kordyl et al. 2025). Investigations in the MN technology field include using different materials to fabricate MNs, delivering various molecules, employing different MN types, and evaluating the clinical applications and future prospects of this technology (Chudzińska et al. 2024; Abudoleh et al. 2025). However, at present, there are no pharmaceutical MN products available in the Jordanian market.

To translate MNs from research to industry and the clinical market, several questions and concerns need to be addressed. MNs are designed to overcome the physical barrier of the skin to deliver molecules to the viable epidermis. Since MNs pierce the skin, this might allow exogenous molecules and bioburdens to enter the body (Khalid et al. 2023). As a counselling tip, patients should be advised to sterilize or clean the area of application, which may reduce the incidence of bioburden penetration. It is important to note that the risk of microbial or bioburden passage is greater with conventional hypodermic needles compared to MNs (Donnelly et al. 2009).

Conclusion

Given that microneedles (MNs) have not yet entered the commercial market, it is noteworthy that pharmacists have demonstrated a commendable level of comprehension regarding this pioneering technology. However, it is crucial to address certain knowledge gaps that persist in their understanding. Several key aspects merit attention, as MNs

have exhibited a remarkable capability to penetrate the outermost layer of the skin effectively and painlessly, facilitating the efficient delivery of therapeutic agents. Furthermore, MNs have found application in a wide spectrum of medical scenarios, spanning acute and chronic conditions, hormonal therapy, vaccine delivery, and catering to diverse age groups. Consequently, it is imperative to recommend heightened efforts toward educating pharmacists in this domain, ensuring they are well equipped to navigate the potential future integration of MNs in clinical practice.

To facilitate the integration of microneedle technology into clinical practice, a multifaceted approach is necessary. This should involve regulatory advancements, manufacturing standards, comprehensive education for pharmacists, and robust patient education strategies. Pharmacists are positioned to be at the forefront of this integration, ensuring the safe, effective, and widespread adoption of microneedle drug and vaccine products. They play a crucial role in patient education and can provide comprehensive guidance on the use of microneedles. This includes explaining how drugs are delivered through microneedles, demonstrating proper administration techniques, and outlining necessary precautions. Pharmacists should also advise on the appropriate storage conditions for microneedles, how to interpret labeling information, and the importance of adhering to expiry dates for each microneedle patch. Through these concerted efforts, microneedle technology has the potential to revolutionize drug delivery and significantly enhance patient care.

What is already known about this topic?

Microneedle technology constitutes a pioneering subject in drug delivery research. Research efforts have substantiated the effectiveness and adaptability of microneedles for transdermal and intradermal therapeutic delivery. Initially introduced to the public and pharmacists as a cosmetic technique, notably under the designation “dermaroller” and similar terms, microneedle technology has since evolved beyond its cosmetic applications.

What does this article add?

Microneedle technology has gained significant attention for transdermal or intradermal delivery of vaccines and therapeutic agents. Despite its potential, regulatory approval for microneedle technology is currently pending,

leading to an absence of available products in the pharmaceutical market and non-dispensation by pharmacists. This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge, opinions, and behaviors of Jordanian pharmacists regarding this innovative technology. The findings contribute to the assessment of pharmacist awareness, enabling experts in the microneedle field to address knowledge gaps and enhance understanding, thereby facilitating the advancement of this technology.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives: This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee at Isra University, Amman, Jordan (SREC/22/12/64). Informed consent was obtained from all study participants. All methods were carried out in accordance with relevant guidelines and regulations of the Declaration of Helsinki.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

All authors contributed to the conceptualization, methodology, data analysis, writing, and review of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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